

Prithvi Sukta- A Study from Arena of evolution point of View

Bhakti Bhavana Mishra

Ph.D. Research Scholar,

Department of Sanskrit, Utkal University,

Vani Vihar, Bhubaneswar, Odisha – 751004

Abstract

Prithvi Sukta, which is part of the Atharva Veda, is in the tradition of hymns to the forces of nature. The Prithvi Sukta has an entire hymn of sixty three verses dedicated to Mother Earth. It presents ecofriendly ideas to understand the treasures of planet earth and means to exploit and utilize them in a sustainable manner. Thus, the Prithive Sukta considers the progress of human civilization as part of the progress of the whole universe or ecosphere. It also shows how our earth system with its complex inter-linkages between the atmosphere, the hydrosphere, the biosphere and the ecosphere provides us with resources, land resources, energy resources, and many other ecological resources.

This topics tries to explore how the ideas presented in the Prithvi Sukta in Atharva Veda can be made relevant for the present ecological issues. It is Always a good gesture for an employee to speak in favour of his organization. Prithvi Sukta too advocates all the humans to converse in favour of their mother, Land. In addition, the hymn emphasizes on the availability of land for progress. It reveals the kind of activities to be done on the land. It identifies the benefits of proper usage of the land. It distinguishes various biomes on the earth and highlights their necessity. Thus, Prithvi Sukta exhibits the visionary of ancient Indian seers which is much similar to that of a professional managerial genius with eco-friendly consciousness. Few such interesting aspects from managerial point of view are presented in this paper.

Key words:

Prithvisukta, Healthy Society, Mother Earth, Maintenance, Trade, Consumption

1. INTRODUCTION

Prithvi Sukta is present in Atharva Veda. Atharva Veda is also called as Atharvangiro Veda, Brahma Veda, Bhishag Veda and Kshatra Veda. There are as many as 20 Kandas, 730 Suktas and 36 Prapathakas and 5987 Mantras in Atharva Veda. Prithvi Sukta is the first one in 12th Kanda, with 63 Mantras in it.

Nowadays, we consider the English word 'Earth' to be an equivalent expression for the word Prithivi. Let us take it granted for the time being.

The Earth according to the modern science is solely one of the planets; that moves around the Sun, sheltering a wide variety of living organisms as its solitary specialty.

As far as Indian tradition is concerned, right from the times of Veda, Prithivi is the mother of mothers. Indians developed an emotional attachment with Prithivi. Number of legendary stories in the Vedas, Itihasas and Puranas are evident in support of these emotions. A story describes that the Prithivi is the daughter of emperor Prithu and another story describes that the Prithivi is the mother of Sita Devi, an ideal Indian woman.

Prithvi Sukta, a hymn in AtharvaVeda, avows very clearly that, the Land is the Mother of the entire biosphere. Indian ancestors understood this truth and proclaimed it –

माता भूमिः पुत्रो अहं पृथिव्याः ।¹

“Land is my mother. I am the son of the land.” Mother is the one who conceives, generates, feeds, trains and makes her progeny independent.

सा नो भूमिर्विसृजतां माता पुत्राय मे पयः ।²

“May the land, our mother, release milk for me.” If one observes the above sentences carefully, it is understood that these are the activities of a modern organization with a methodological expression called recruitment of human resources. That is why often an employee calls an organization as his mother organization where he was recruited, worked and learned earlier, in his career. Indian tradition insisted on the following characteristics in acknowledgement of a healthy society:

काले वर्षतु पर्जन्यः पृथिवी सस्यशालिनी ।
देशोऽयं क्षोभरहितो ब्राह्मणाः सन्तु निर्भयाः ।
अपुत्राः पुत्रिणः सन्तु पुत्रिणः सन्तु पौत्रिणः ।
अधनाः सधनाः सन्तु जीवन्तु शरदां शतम् ।

- i. May the cloud rain in right time.
- ii. May the earth be repleted with plants and food grains.
- iii. May the country be free from calamities.
- iv. May the Brahmins be fearless.
- v. May the people without progeny beget progeny.
- vi. The people with progeny be grandparents.
- vii. May the poor be rich.
- viii. May all live for hundred years.

Indeed, the above are the goals, set for a king to achieve. Achievement of goals is possible sans all doubts, with good Management only.

Bhartrihari, a great ancient poet, who was believed to be the elder brother of king Vikrama, encouraged the Kings to carefully nurture the people, if they wanted to gain various kinds of prosperity from their kingdom. He compared the kingdom to a cow and the people to her calf. The cowherd is supposed to nourish the calf with love and care, for he wanted to get the milk from the cow.

राजन् दुधुक्षसि यदि क्षितिधेनुमेनां
तेनाद्य वत्समिव लोकममुं पुषाण ।
तस्मिंश्च सम्यगनिशं परिपुष्यमाणे
नानाफलं पलति कल्पलतेव भूमिः ॥³

Thus, Bhartrihari too supported the concept of Mother – Child relation between the Earth and Human beings. The term ‘Land’ in the vision of a developer, is often used in an extensive sense. It does not denote merely the exterior of the earth, but it also includes all those natural resources which are the complimentary contributions of the nature. Ascertainment of the available and exploitable resources before investing or before acquiring those resources is always necessary for an organizer. It is recommended in the Sukta that the Land is not only the richest among all the existing resources, but the base for the rest.

These natural resources or gifts include Forests, Mountains Rivers and Oceans etc. Land is the base for various elements of the atmosphere like the Air, Heat of the Sun, Light, Climate, Weather, Rainfall; etc. Land is the chest of various minerals above and under its surface such as iron, coal, copper and even water.

गिरयस्ते पर्वता हिमवन्तोऽरण्यं ते पृथिवि स्योमस्तु ।⁴

“O Land! May your hills, snowcapped mountains, forests be comfortable for us.”

बभ्रुं कृष्णं रोहिणीं विश्वरुपां ध्रुवां भूमिं पृथिवीमिन्द्रगुप्ताम् ।

अजीतोऽहतो अक्षतोऽध्यष्टां पृथिवीमहम् ॥⁵

“May I Stay unconquered, unsuited and unwounded on the Earth, which is brown, black, red and multi-coloured, protected by Indra?”

Here, the word अजीतः (unconquered) does not merely indicate the wish of an entrepreneur who wants to possess absolute ownership rights over his land but indicates even his wish even to win a considerable share in the market by competing against the rivals. The words अहतः (unsmitten) and अक्षतः (unwounded) indicate that the entrepreneur needs good legal protection. Indra indeed is the implementer of the Law. The colours are the indicators of the various kinds of lands with varied fertility and variety of rich minerals. The words अहम् अध्यष्टाम् indicate the wish of the entrepreneur that he wants to make habitat everywhere, where one can survive with good livelihood on the land.

Thus, we can consider that, these lines of the Sukta give the modern entrepreneurs to see these necessary conditions are satisfied before launching their new venture in a new place:

- i) Location of the land must be confirmed well. (Whether it is located on the hills, or on the shore of a sea, or in the middle of a sea, or in a forest, or in or near a habitat of the people with purchasing

- power etc. So, that it will be easy to decide what kind of trade or industry can attract sufficient profits.)
- ii) Type of the land must be confirmed suitable to the type of venture. (Whether the land is suitable for agriculture or for mining or for building a theme National Journal of Hindi & Sanskrit Research ~17~ park etc.)
 - iii) Healthy competition is prevailing and there are no tough obstacles like red tapism and demands for bribe etc.
 - iv) The business Law is safeguarded by a commanding authority.

2. THE PRINCIPLE OF ESTABLISHMENT, MAINTENANCE AND SUSPENSION

The Modern Management considers the Land as a Free Gift of the Nature and confirms that it is not produced by the human beings. However, Prithvi Sukta declares that the Earth is sustained by the Great Truth, Daunting Divine Order, Intense Fortitude, Penance and Brahman and Sacrifice.

सत्यं बृहद्वृतमुग्रं दीक्षा तपो ब्रह्म यज्ञः पृथीर्वी धारयन्ति ।⁶

Here, sustenance is establishment, maintenance and suspension as well. In the process of sustaining, an organization is supposed to set up machinery for production purpose, supposed to properly maintain it for making good benefits out of it and even supposed to dispose it off, when it is not necessary anymore. Brahma, the almighty is said to be the sustainer of the wholesome. According Sankhya philosophy, the so called nature is the invariable expansion of Prakriti. Expansion takes places only when Purusha and Prakriti get contact with each other. Though it is not mentioned anywhere in Sankhya theory, but as humans we do perceive, the creation is true. So, the power that brings both Prakriti and Purusha may be called as सत्यम् – Truth and बृहद्वृतम् – Daunting Divine Order. The modern management too considers that the land is not the production of human beings as Indian ancestors did.

तपस् (Penance) is required for maintenance. Besides one's determination, Physical Labour, Oral dexterity, and Intellectual Foresight are required for the successful maintenance of an organization. These three are respectively called as शारीरं तपः (Physical Tapas), वाङ्मयं तपः (Oral Tapas) and मानसं तपः (Intellectual Tapas).

The following is शारीरं तपः - The Physical Tapas.

देवद्विजगुरुप्राज्ञपूजनं शौचमार्जवम् ।

ब्रह्मचर्यमहिंसा च शारीरं तप उच्यते ।⁷

Deva Dvija Guru Prajna Pujanam can be defined here as honouring the instructions of the superiors of various levels. Saucha can be defined as Keeping the working place and environment clean. Arjava can be defined as Cooperation and teamwork. Brahmacharya can be defined as strictly sticking to one's own assigned duty.

Ahimsa can be defined as peaceful coexistence with the organization i.e., having a clear mind that working for the benefits of the organization is ultimately for one's own benefits.

This is the Tapas of bottom level people of an organization. The following is वाङ्मयं तपः (Oral Tapas)-

अनुद्वेगकरं वाक्यं सत्यं प्रियहितं च यत् ।

स्वाध्यायाभ्यासनं चैव वाङ्मयं तप उच्यते ॥⁸

Anudvegakaram vakyam can be defined as skillful words spoken in favour both labourers and superiors. Satyam can be defined as precise reports. Priya Hitam can be defined as balancing the interests of employer and employees and preserving good relations with both. Svadhyayaabhyasanam can be defined as keeping oneself updated with the ever-changing techniques and technologies, and recommending and implementing the best suitable ones to the organization.

This is the Tapas of the middle level people in an organization. The following is मानसं तपः (Intellectual Tapas)-

मनः प्रसादः सौम्यत्वं मौनमात्मविनिग्रहः ।

भावसंशुद्धिरित्येतत् तपो मानसमुच्यते ॥⁹

Manah prasada can be defined as keeping oneself cool even in tense situation. Saumyatva can be defined as Understanding the worries of one's own employees and ensuing as a generous benefactor. Maunam can be defined as speaking not more than required. Atmavinigraha can be defined as remaining firm and bold even during the crises. Bhavasamsuddhi can be defined as a genuine wish to help oneself, by providing livelihood to many and thus, contributing to the development of one's own nation by setting up an organization. This is the Tapas of highest level people in an organization.

The above mentioned Bhavasamsuddhi is complete when यज्ञः (Sacrifice) is performed. The influence of Yajna is described in Padmapurana:

यज्ञेनाप्यायिता देवा वृष्टुत्सर्गेण मानवाः ।

आप्यायनं वै कुर्वन्ति यज्ञाः कल्याणहेतवः ॥¹⁰

Devas are nourished by Yajnas. In return, humans are cherished by rains. By delivering such nourishment and cherishing, Yajnas are favourable to all the living creatures in the world." In Modern times, a Yajna (Sacrifice) can be

defined as nourishing the treasury of the Government by sincere and regular payment of taxes and getting cherished by the favourable organizational policies, designed by the Government. By receiving good amount of taxes, the Government can do something good for all the citizens.

3. ACCLAMATION OF THE NEED OF TRADE

It is the duty of the Government to provide facilities to those entrepreneurs who would promote employment and could add to the prosperity of the state. Prithvi Sukta hails the Management of Roads in a state. Good roads lead not merely to the destinations of the people, but they can even define the destiny of a country.

The Government should lay good roads for the moment of chariots, carts and other vehicles. The seers praised the earth for having such roads.

ये ते पन्थानो बहवो जनायना रथस्य वर्तानसश्च यातवे ।¹¹

It is again, the duty of the Kings to see that those roads, “which could be properly used or misused by various people, are to be maintained with proper security.”

4. CONSUMPTION MANAGEMENT

Electricity is either being produced or bought and sold by the modern Governments by fixing meters in the houses of consumers. It has become an age old practice. But, now-a-days, as a part of consumption management, the Government has begun fixing meters to measure the water consumption of its citizens. This is the result of imprudent consumption of natural resources from the past few decades. Though it is called as consumption management as a sugar coat, it is indeed a bitter pill. It is an unfortunate situation of selling one of the essentials to the people. However, the topic of consumption management was discussed and implemented by Indians many ages ago. Prithvi Sukta also makes a mention of it. The following is the humble prayer of the seer to his mother, the Earth:

“O Earth! Let that quickly grow over, what all I dig out from you. Let me hit neither your vitals nor your heart.”

5. CONCLUSION

Thus, the wisdom of the Indian seers as good managers is proven in Prithvi Sukta. They always stood on the side of the good, better and best options for the welfare of the world. They were always rational, and never spoke anything blindly. They never thought that the world is separate from their family. They trusted in वसुधैव कुटुम्बकम् (Universal Family) and considered the Earth as their mother. They had given equal priority to establishment, maintenance and disposal as well. Incarnation of Rama, Behaviour of Rama and Departure of Rama in the Ramayana are the perfect examples for it. It is applicable even to an organization, to meet the changing demands of the time. They had recognized the need of the distributor of the prosperity and encouraged trade. They recognized the importance of a potential system for the exploitation of natural resources. However, the modern education makes Indians think irrationally and makes them feel inferior to western people. Unfortunately, simple life has become an object of laughter, and exploiting everything and everybody has become an icon for intelligence. May such tendency be wiped off by the study of Ancient Indian Scriptures.

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